

Screening of Soil-Derived Fungi for Protease Production

Santosh G. Shere^{1*} and Madhukar S. Wadikar²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Botany, Deogiri College. Chh. Sambhajinagar (Aurangabad)-431005.

²Professor and Head, Department of Botany, R. B. Attal Arts, Science and Commerce College, Georai, Dist- Beed-431127.

*Corresponding author: santoshshere1994@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In the present study an attempt has been made for the isolation of potent Protease enzyme producing fungi. About thirty-seven fungi were isolated from soil sample and screen for protease production on potato dextrose agar (PDA) media amended with different protease substrates like Skim Milk Agar (SMA), Casein Agar and Gelatin. Positive fungi shows hydrolysis on substrates.

Keywords: Protease, Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), Skim Milk Agar (SMA), Casein, Gelatin,

INTRODUCTION

Proteases are a group of enzymes whose catalytic function is to hydrolysed proteins. They are also known as proteolytic enzymes or proteinases. Proteases belong to a major class of enzymes that play a crucial role in both physiological processes and commercial applications. They represent one of the three largest groups of industrial enzymes and account for approximately 60% of total worldwide enzyme sales. (Rao *et al.*, 1998).

For the microbial and biological activities soil is a dynamic medium and the number and kind of microorganisms present in soil depends on environmental factors (Prescott *et al.*, 1993). Microorganisms are the most common sources of commercial enzymes due to their physiological and biochemical properties, facile culture conditions and ease of cell manipulation (Dias *et al.*, 2010).

Proteases represent one of the three largest groups of industrial enzymes and find application in detergents, leather industry, food industry, pharmaceutical industry and bioremediation processes. Proteolytic enzymes are very important in digestion as they breakdown the peptide bonds in the protein foods to liberate the amino acids needed by the body (Ogino *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, Proteolytic enzymes have long been utilized in various therapeutic applications. Their medical relevance is supported by numerous clinical studies highlighting their benefits in oncology, inflammatory disorders, blood

rheology regulation, and immune system modulation. These enzymes also demonstrate the ability to break down protein-based structures found in pathogens such as parasites, fungi, and bacteria, contributing to their potential as supportive agents in antimicrobial and antiparasitic therapies. (Coelho *et al.*, 1978).

According to a recent study, the vast majority of industrial enzymes currently used are hydrolytic in action and are used in the degradation of natural materials. Protease enzymes remained the dominant type because they are used by the vast majority of industries. Microorganisms are the most common source of commercial enzymes due to the nature of their physiology and biochemistry, facile cultural conditions, and ease of manipulation of the cells. Moreover, the fungus is generally considered a good strain for the production of protease enzymes. They are simpler to regenerate from mould fermentation broth of the genus *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Rhizopus* (Vishwanatha *et al.*, 2009; Kumar and Jain, 2017).

There has been a renewed interest in the study of proteolytic enzymes, largely due to the growing recognition of their critical roles in cellular metabolic processes and their increasing relevance in industrial applications. Among these, extracellular proteases are of particular commercial significance, as they have found widespread use across various industrial sectors. Their versatility and efficiency make them valuable tools in industries such as food processing, pharmaceuticals, detergents, and leather manufacturing.

COLLECTION OF SOIL SAMPLE:

Soil samples were collected from Chh. Sambhajinagar, (Aurangabad) Marathwada region (MH). The soil samples were collected from a depth of about 15 cm with the help of sterilized spatula in sterile zip lock polyethylene bags and well labelled with collection site. (Oyelekee *et al.*, 2010).

ISOLATION OF SOIL FUNGI:

Fungi were found by serial dilution agar plate method as described earlier by Waksman (1922). 1gm of each of the soil sample was separately added in test tube containing 9 ml of sterile distilled water followed by vortexing for 10 minutes to make soil suspension of 10^{-1} dilution. 1ml of soil suspension from 10^{-1} dilution was transferred in another test tube containing 9 ml of

sterile distilled water to prepare 10^{-2} dilution. This step (withdrawal and transfer of soil suspension) was repeated until the preparation of 10^{-6} dilution. 0.1 ml of each of the soil dilution (10^{-1} to 10^{-6}) was aseptically inoculated and uniformly spreaded in sterile Petri plate containing the potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium (Sinha *et al.*, 2013). Streptomycin was added to the Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium just before pouring it into Petri plates in order to inhibit bacterial growth. The inoculated potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates were then incubated at 28°C for five days. Fungal colonies that appeared on the plates were subsequently purified by point inoculation onto fresh potato dextrose agar (PDA) plates.

SCREENING OF PROTEASE PRODUCING FUNGI

Fungal isolates obtained on PDA plates were screened for proteolytic activity using casein agar (Sethi 2015). The composition of the casein agar medium (gm/L) was: casein – 1.0 gm, KH_2PO_4 – 1.0 gm, MgSO_4 – 2.0 gm, agar – 30.0 gm, with the pH adjusted to 8.5. To inhibit bacterial growth, streptomycin was added at a concentration of 10 mg/L. The composition of the skim milk agar medium (gm/L) was: skim milk powder – 28.0 gm, casein enzymatic hydrolysate – 5.0 gm, yeast extract – 2.5 gm, dextrose – 1.0 gm, and agar – 15.0 gm. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 7.2 before sterilization. The composition of gelatin agar medium (gm/L) is as follows: gelatin 30gm, casein enzymatic hydrolysate 10gm, sodium chloride 10gm, agar 15gm and pH was adjusted to 7.2. The fungal isolates were individually incubated at 28°C for 3–4 days. After incubation the plates were examined for the presence of clear zones around the fungal colonies indicating protease activity. For gelatin agar plates the zone of hydrolysis was observed after flooding the plates with a mercury chloride solution, which helps visualize gelatin degradation. (Arun Kumar Sharma *et al.*, 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of fungal strains producing protease enzyme from the soil sample was collected from Marathwada region (MH). The isolation of fungi was done on Potato Dextrose Agar media (PDA). Fungal isolates were screened by the growth on three different Protease producing substrates i.e skim milk agar, casein agar and gelatin agar media. Protease producing fungi were identified by the appearance of clear zone of hydrolysis around colonies. We have tested 37 fungal

isolates on skim milk agar, casein agar and gelatin agar plate. Out of 37 fungal isolates AG09, BD09, ND09, BD19, LT17, LT22, HG04, PR02, BD01, JL16, PR23, AU18, ND07, AU24, ND17, OS11, LT06, LT25, AU16 and PR16 shown positive response on these three substrates. Among these 14 isolates were found

positive on skim milk agar plate, 13 isolates were found positive on casein agar plate and 11 isolates were found positive on gelatin agar plate. LT06 shows positive response on Skim milk like that PR02, ND07, AU16 only respond on casein and BD01, AU24 only shows positive activity on Gelatin media plates.

Table 1: Sample showing Positive response on Different substrate

Sr. No	Culture Code	Skim Milk Agar Media	Casein Media	Gelatin Media
01	AU09	++++	+++	++
02	BD09	+++	-	+
03	AU13	-	-	-
04	OS24	-	-	-
05	ND09	++	+++	-
06	BD19	+++	+++	-
07	OS10	-	-	-
08	LT17	++++	-	++++
09	LT22	+	+++	-
10	PR03	-	-	-
11	HG04	+++	++++	+++
12	JL12	-	-	-
13	PR02	-	+	-
14	OS02	-	-	-
15	BD01	-	-	++
16	JL16	++++	+++	-
17	OS14	-	-	-
18	PR19	-	-	-
19	PR23	+	-	+++
20	AU18	+++	-	+
21	HG02	-	-	-
22	ND07	-	++	-
23	HG14	-	-	-
24	AU24	-	-	+++
25	LT11	-	-	-
26	ND17	++++	+++	++++
27	ND23	-	-	-
28	OS11	++	+++	+
29	ND25	-	-	-
30	LT06	+++	-	-
31	JL32	-	-	-
32	HG03	-	-	-
33	LT25	+++	++	+++
34	AU16	-	+	-
35	LT24	-	-	-
36	OS08	-	-	-
37	PR16	++++	+++	-

++++very good, +++ good, ++small, + very small Hydrolytic zone

Fig 1: Screening of protease using different substrate (A) Skim milk agar (B) Casein (C) Gelatine

The fungus AU09, HG04, ND17, OS11 and LT25 showing hydrolytic zone in all three substrates suggesting higher protease activity and broad substrate specificity.

CONCLUSION

This work state that the qualitative plate test assay can be effective for predicting extracellular protease producing. In view of the results obtained, it can be concluded that this study indicate that new novel protease producers could be discovered from environmental samples by very simple plate-test screening method.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to **Santosh G. Shere**

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